

Original Research

Digital Bookkeeping Adoption among MSMEs in Indonesia: Extension of Technology Acceptance Model

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Abstract

Digital bookkeeping is an important innovation for micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in managing business finances. The purpose of this study is to examine the factors that influence the intention to use digital bookkeeping applications. This study uses the Technology Acceptance Model and expands with self-efficacy and personal awareness of user intention to use digital bookkeeping applications. The sample of this study was 225 SMEs from various types of industrial sectors, and was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) through Smart PLS. The results showed that perceived ease of use and self-efficacy affect MSMEs' intention to use digital bookkeeping, while perceived usefulness and personal awareness have no effect. This research provides insight in developing knowledge related to technology adoption in the financial sector, and contributes to the expansion of the Technology Acceptance Model with self-efficacy and personal awareness. Practically, this research has implications in creating good financial management for MSMEs.

Keywords: Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, personal awareness, self-efficacy, TAM.

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Introduction

ASEAN Member States' economic growth and development are dependent upon Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs). MSMEs make significant regional contributions of 85% to employment, 44.8% to GDP, and 18% to national exports. The cumulative number of MSMEs that have formally enrolled their enterprises on the OSS platform has amounted to 8.71 million units as of 2022. Product competitiveness on the global market can be enhanced, as well as productivity and quality of the workforce can be improved, by expediting the digitization of MSMEs. By digitalizing Indonesia's abundant natural resources and resilient labor force, this country's potential for producing high-value-added goods and integrating seamlessly into digital platforms can be fully realized. Assuring the growth and sustainability of their businesses in the current digital era is an additional reason why MSMEs are transitioning to digitalization, not merely to follow trends.

With one thousand MSME participants as its objective, the digitalisation program represents an exceptionally audacious effort to promote digital adaptation for business growth. The efficacy of the program from the previous year, which furnished guidance and instruction to 1,077 MSMEs indicates that these endeavors are effectively fortifying the MSME sector. It is impossible to overstate the significance of MSME participants' active engagement in this program, as it will enable them to adapt to the digital age and contribute effectively to the digital economy (Firman El Amny Azra, 2020).

Financial transaction recording is one area in which technology adoption in MSMEs can be implemented, and the adoption of digital bookkeeping successfully is contingent on a number of factors. Perceived ease of use pertains to the extent to which an individual considers an information system to be convenient and devoid of substantial cognitive exertion in its operation (Davis, 1989). An individual's inclination to utilize digital bookkeeping will be influenced by perceived ease of use (Zebua & Widuri, 2023). The findings of a study conducted in India indicate that digital bookkeeping is influenced by both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Liébana-Cabanillas et al., 2020).

Davis (1989) defines perceived usefulness as the degree to which an individual holds the belief that utilising a specific system will enhance their job performance. Individuals are more inclined to adopt a new technology if they perceive its benefits to outweigh the effort required to adopt it (Sulistyowati et al., 2021). This will have a substantial impact on the behavioral intentions of users of digital bookkeeping (Zebua & Widuri, 2023). The findings of a study conducted in Iran by Ashrafi et al., (2020) indicate that the adoption of digital bookkeeping is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, but not satisfaction. Perceived enjoyment has an impact, while attitude towards something has no effect (Ashrafi et al., 2020). According to a study conducted in Pakistan by Saleem et al., (2022), the adoption of digital bookkeeping is influenced by the perception of its usefulness. According to a study conducted in Indonesia by Zebua & Widuri (2023), the utilization of technology is influenced by the perceptions of its usefulness and ease of use.

The primary obstacle encountered by MSMEs in Indonesia when seeking business capital assistance is the absence of financial documentation that demonstrates the

company's performance. Digital bookkeeping is a technological advancement that allows MSMEs to organize their firm financial records online. This enables MSMEs to easily track the progress of their organization. However, MSMEs lack the confidence to embrace new technologies like digital bookkeeping, despite being aware of the significance of financial records. Prior research has utilized TAM to examine the uptake of particular technologies, yielding incongruous findings. Studies that incorporate self-efficacy and personal awareness into the “Technology Acceptance Model” to examine the adoption of digital bookkeeping is still lacking. The theoretical contribution of this study is to extend “TAM” with self-efficacy and personal awareness. This relates to the importance of confidence possessed by MSMEs that they can do digital business bookkeeping, and realize that financial records are important. practically, this study contributes to MSMEs being able to do digital bookkeeping in analyzing their business development. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to predict MSMEs' intention to adopt digital bookkeeping. The research question posed in this study is how the influence of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, self-efficacy and personal awareness in predicting the adoption of digital bookkeeping.

Literature Review

Technology Acceptance Model utilized to analyze and comprehend the diverse factors that impact users' acceptance of the intention to utilize technology (Davis, 1989). It is believed to be capable of explaining and predicting the acceptance of technology by users in terms of their intention to use the technology, and “TAM” is utilized in this study. Furthermore, Ming & Jais (2022) elucidates that “TAM” has evolved and progressed akin to an organic entity through the loss of its initial structure. To clarify, “TAM” has undergone multiple iterations of development in order to establish a more comprehensive and established understanding (Putri et al., 2023). Davis (1989) discovered that perceived convenience had a substantial impact on the intention to adopt information technology after they added it to the original “TAM”. Davis (1989) formulated a “technology acceptance model” that serves to elucidate the user's behavior with regard to technology acceptance. Although “TAM” is formulated on the basis of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), not all TRA components are incorporated.

Davis (1989) restricts the inclusion of the belief and attitude components to the exclusion of normative beliefs and subjective norms. Information technology usage behavior is influenced by individuals' initial perceptions of the technology's benefits and ease of use (Davis, 1989). Both of these perceptions constitute a component of belief when linked to TRA. This research employs the behavioral model and MSMEs' perspectives to examine the utilization of digital bookkeeping on mobile-based financial records. However, it further incorporates perceived convenience as a predictor of businesses' intention to disclose information voluntarily while completing the questionnaire, as well as perceived usefulness and ease of use by MSMEs.

The concept of perceived ease of use refers to an individual's level of assurance regarding the potential enhancement of their job performance through the utilization of a specific system. As stated by Davis (1989) that user-friendliness is enhanced by the proliferation of new technologies, including mobile internet, internet banking, and

smartphone technology. An individual's inclination to utilize digital bookkeeping will be influenced by the system ease (Zebua & Widuri, 2023).

Davis (1989) defines perceived usefulness as the degree to which an individual holds the belief that utilizing a specific system will enhance their job performance. Individuals are more inclined to adopt new technology if they perceive its benefits to outweigh the effort required to acquire it. This will have a substantial impact on the behavioral intentions of users of digital bookkeeping (Zebua & Widuri, 2023).

Perceived self-efficacy refers to an individual's conviction regarding their ability to execute a specific behavior safely and effectively (Daragmeh et al., 2021). The study demonstrates superiority over other “technology acceptance models” in comprehending continued behavior towards a specific system in order to ascertain users' continued intention to use mobile wallets in the context of COVID-19. Research in Arabia by Mujalli et al., (2022) shows that self-efficacy influences the use of virtual account e-wallets.

Personal awareness of security refers to the degree to which users or clients believe that submitting financial and personal information online is secure for the purpose of conducting transactions (Saleem et al., 2022). As a result, the perceptions of online shoppers are predominantly shaped by their own consciousness. Perceptions, attitudes, and intentions regarding online purchases are positively influenced by a sense of security when conducting such transactions (Saleem et al., 2022). The personal awareness of consumers exerts the greatest influence on their perceptions of online purchases. Perceptions, attitudes, and intentions regarding online purchases are positively influenced by a sense of security when conducting such transactions (Saleem et al., 2022).

Hypothesis Development

Perceived usefulness and intention to use digital bookkeeping

Davis (1989) defines perceived usefulness as the degree to which an individual holds the belief that utilizing a specific system will enhance their job performance. Individuals are more inclined to adopt a new technology if they perceive its benefits to outweigh the effort required to adopt it (Sulistyowati et al., 2020). The behavioral intentions of users will be profoundly impacted by this (Zebua & Widuri, 2023). Based on the aforementioned explanation, it can be concluded that perceived usefulness has a substantial positive impact on intention to use digital bookkeeping. Several previous studies in Iran, India, Pakistan and Indonesia (Ashrafi et al., 2020; Liébana-Cabanillas et al., 2020; Saleem et al., 2022; Zebua & Widuri, 2023) confirmed the importance of perceived usefulness.

H₁: Perceived usefulness has a positive effect on the intention to use digital bookkeeping

Perceived ease of use and intention to use digital bookkeeping

The concept of perceived ease of use refers to an individual's level of assurance regarding the potential enhancement of their job performance through the utilization of a

specific system (Davis, 1989). User-friendliness is enhanced by the proliferation of new technologies, including mobile internet, internet banking, and smartphone technology. An individual's intention to utilize technology will be influenced by system easiness (Zebua & Widuri, 2023). According to the preceding explanation, perceived ease of use has a substantial positive effect on intention to use digital bookkeeping. Much research has demonstrated that perceived ease of use has an effect on the intention to use a specific system. A study in Iran by Ashrafi et al., (2020) with the number of 169 respondents shows that perceived ease of use has potential effect. Study in India by Liébana-Cabanillas et al., (2020) of 70 respondents shows that perceived ease of use has an effect on the intention to use m-payment. Study in Pakistan by Saleem et al., (2022) with the number of 500 respondents shows that perceived ease of use has an effect on the intention to use e-shopping. Study in Indonesia by Zebua & Widuri, (2023) with 253 respondents shows that perceived ease of use has an effect on cloud accounting adoption.

H₂: Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on Intention of digital bookkeeping

Self-efficacy and intention to use digital bookkeeping

Perceived self-efficacy refers to an individual's conviction regarding their ability to execute a specific behavior with success (Daragmeh et al., 2021). The study examines preemptive behavior using TCT, which integrates HBM and demonstrates superiority over other “technology acceptance models” in comprehending users' continuation behavior towards a specific system in order to ascertain their intention to continue using mobile wallets in the context of COVID-19. Certain scholars have employed TCT to ascertain users' intention to continue utilizing banking and payment systems; ECM uses satisfaction as the primary determinant of users' intention to continue utilizing the technology; and “TAM” suggests perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as the primary determinants of users' intention to continue utilizing a technology in order to examine users' acceptance of it. According to the preceding explanation, awareness has a substantial positive effect on the intention to use digital bookkeeping.

The study conducted in Indonesia by Marbun et al., (2020) demonstrates that the implementation of digital bookkeeping is influenced by self-efficacy. The study conducted in Hungary by Daragmeh et al., (2021) involved 1080 academics from three distinct universities who utilized electronic wallets throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. The research findings indicate that self-efficacy influences the adoption of e-wallets.

H₃: Self-Efficacy has a positive effect on Intention of digital bookkeeping

Personal awareness and intention to use digital bookkeeping

Personal Awareness is a communication strategy that motivates consumers to adopt new technologies by informing them of their benefits and applications (Singh & Sinha, 2020). MSMEs that have a high level of technological awareness will not be apprehensive about implementing new technologies. A consumer whose concerns include the potential loss of personal data, third-party control over personal information, and third-party misuse of data will consistently strive to restrict their technology usage, thereby influencing their intention to adopt said technology. The majority of the influence on

consumers' perceptions of online purchases comes from their own awareness. Perceptions, attitudes, and intentions regarding online purchases are positively influenced by a sense of security when conducting such transactions (Saleem et al., 2022). According to the preceding explanation, awareness has a substantial positive effect on the intention to use digital bookkeeping. A study conducted in Pakistan by Saleem et al., (2022), and Singh & Sinha (2020) shows that personal awareness has an effect on the specific system.

H4: Personal awareness has a positive effect on the intention to use digital bookkeeping

The following is the proposed model in this study:

Figure 1. Proposed Model

Methodology

The population in this study were MSME players in the Cirebon area, with a sample of MSMEs from various types of industrial sectors. In this study, 225 valid samples were processed according to the data collected. This research uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis through Smart PLS. The stages in data analysis include: outer model analysis, inner model analysis and hypothesis testing. This research uses a quantitative approach with data collection through questionnaires to obtain the perceptions of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) regarding the use of digital bookkeeping to record financial transactions. Intention to use digital bookkeeping was measured by four (4) items (Mohamad Zain et al., 2023), perceived usefulness four (4) items (Ashrafi et al., 2020; Kasilingam, 2020), perceived ease of use six (6) items (Esfahbodi et al., 2022; Liébana-Cabanillas et al., 2020), self-efficacy five (5) items (Daragmeh et al., 2021), and personal awareness three (3) items (Saleem et al., 2022). An interval scale was used to measure respondents' answers with numbers 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Results

The highest age of respondents is 21-30 years (56%). Based on business age, the majority of respondents' businesses were <5 years old as many as 133 respondents (59.1%), the majority of respondents had a high school education (47.6%). Judging from the industrial sector, the majority of respondents have businesses in the food sector as much as 72.00%, the beverage sector as much as 5.33%, the goods sector as much as 16.89%, and the service sector as much as 5.78%. Table 1 displays the outcomes of the descriptive analysis, indicating that the respondents' inclination towards utilizing digital bookkeeping earned the most elevated rating. MSME players acknowledge that digital bookkeeping may effectively and methodically assist them in recording their finances. This promotes the inclination to promptly employ digital accounting as opposed to utilizing manual financial records. Furthermore, considerable importance is attributed to the advantages experienced by MSMEs while adopting digital bookkeeping. Meanwhile, the lowest perception of MSMEs among the variables in this study is technology anxiety with a mean value of 3.21.

The Cronbach alpha coefficients for the five primary variables ranged from 0.882 to 0.947, surpassing the threshold of 0.7. Furthermore, the Composite Reliability (CR) values for all variables fell within the range of 0.919 to 0.958, surpassing the threshold of 0.7. These results suggest that the constructs examined in this study demonstrate high levels of dependability. There are two measurement models: one is convergent validity, which is demonstrated through the reliability of the questions, and the other is construct composite reliability (CR) and construct variance retrieved. An acceptable criterion for reliability is that the loading value should exceed 0.70. The average variance extracted (AVE) value is commonly employed to assess convergent validity, with a threshold of 0.50 indicating satisfactory results.

Table 1. Deviation standard, loading, cronbach alpha, CR, AVE

Construction	Item	M	SD	Loading	Cronbach Alpha	CR (>0,7)	AVE (>0,5)
Intention to use	"IU"1	3,94	0,884	0,84	0,882	0,919	0,738
	"IU"2			0,90			
	"IU"3			0,86			
	"IU"4			0,84			
Perceived Ease of Use	"PEoU"1	3,86	0,938	0,79	0,924	0,940	0,725
	"PEoU"2			0,87			
	"PEoU"3			0,83			
	"PEoU"4			0,85			
	"PEoU"5			0,88			
	"PEoU"6			0,87			
Perceived Usefulness	"PU"1	3,93	0,982	0,87	0,910	0,937	0,788
	"PU"2			0,90			
	"PU"3			0,90			
	"PU"4			0,88			

Construction	Item	M	SD	Loading	Cronbach Alpha	CR (>0,7)	AVE (>0,5)
Personal Awareness	“PA”1	3,80	0,867	0,89	0,859	0,914	0,780
	“PA”2			0,86			
	“PA”3			0,89			
Self - Efficacy	“SE”1	3,81	0,935	0,76	0,880	0,913	0,677
	“SE”2			0,77			
	“SE”3			0,87			
	“SE”4			0,86			
	“SE”5			0,84			

Table 2. Discriminant validity results - based on Fornell Larcker Criteria

	Intention to use	Personal Awareness	Perceived Ease of Use	Perceived Usefulness	Self – Efficacy
Intention to use	0,859	0,709	0,727	0,715	0,751
Personal Awareness		0,883	0,688	0,700	0,793
Perceived Ease of Use			0,851	0,827	0,701
Perceived Usefulness				0,888	0,686
Self - Efficacy					0,823

Source: prepared by the author

Figure 2. Structural model evaluation

Tabel 3. Hypothesis testing results H1 - H4

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Deviation Standard (STDEV)	T Statistic (O/STDEV)	P Value	Decision
“PA” ⇒ INT	0,145	0,147	0,083	1,748	0,081	Rejected
“PEOU” ⇒ INT	0,231	0,221	0,105	2,198	0,028	Accepted
“PU” ⇒ INT	0,183	0,183	0,099	1,850	0,065	Rejected
“SE” ⇒ INT	0,349	0,370	0,107	3,250	0,001	Accepted

Tabel 4. R square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
INT	0,663	0,657

Discussion

The results of hypothesis testing show that perceived usefulness has no effect on the intention of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Cirebon to use digital bookkeeping. MSMEs in Cirebon agree that digital bookkeeping can assist MSMEs in completing financial records more quickly. For MSMEs, the use of digital bookkeeping can increase productivity and is useful in recording financial transactions. Digital bookkeeping can also increase the work effectiveness of MSME actors. This result is not in accordance with the “Technology Acceptance Model”. Although MSME actors agree that perceived usefulness is very important to support the use of digital bookkeeping, the fact is that they face obstacles because the majority of MSME actors do not have experience using online financial recording applications. Moreover, they are quite adaptive to technology, such as lack of information and knowledge about digital bookkeeping. This research is consistent with the previous research showing that perceived usefulness has no effect on intention to use specific technology (Semlambo et al., 2022; Tahar et al., 2020; Tambunan, 2023). This research is not in line with other studies that show perceived usefulness has a positive effect on intention to use (Esfahbodi et al., 2022; Saleem et al., 2022; Värzaru et al., 2021).

Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on the interest of MSMEs in Cirebon to use digital bookkeeping. MSMEs state that learning digital bookkeeping is easy, and they believe that interacting with digital bookkeeping is clear and easy to understand. MSMEs are skilled in using digital bookkeeping. For MSMEs, digital bookkeeping can help complete transaction records quickly, thus saving time. Through digital bookkeeping, the condition of MSME business development can be known. This research is consistent with previous research conducted by Hasan & Gupta, (2020) in India, Daragmeh et al., (2021) in Hungary, Liébana-Cabanillas et al., (2020) in India, which shows that perceived ease of use has a positive effect on the use of electronic wallets. The ease of use felt by MSMEs in using digital bookkeeping will lead to the intention of MSMEs to use digital bookkeeping. This result is in accordance with the “Technology Acceptance Model” that if a system is easy to operate and provides benefits to its users, it will increase individual

intention to use the system. This study shows that MSMEs can find it easy to use digital bookkeeping. Therefore, MSMEs give the perception that it is very easy to use digital bookkeeping, so they are interested in using digital bookkeeping.

Self-efficacy has a positive effect on the interest of MSMEs in Cirebon to use digital bookkeeping. Based on the response obtained, MSMEs actors feel confident when using digital bookkeeping even though no one provides direction, they also agree that if they face obstacles, they will contact the digital bookkeeping service provider. Moreover, they agree that if someone provides ways and directions for using digital bookkeeping. Based on the research of Marbun et al., (2020) in Indonesia, Daragmeh et al., (2021) in Hungary, Pourghanbari et al., (2022) in Iran, Mujalli et al., (2022) in Arabia, shows that self-efficacy affects the use of e-wallet virtual accounts. Individual confidence felt by MSMEs in using digital bookkeeping will lead to MSMEs' intention to use digital bookkeeping.

Personal awareness does not affect the intention of MSMEs in Cirebon to use digital bookkeeping. MSMEs feel safe in using digital bookkeeping for financial recording. They also agree that using digital bookkeeping has low risk, and MSMEs also agree that overall, digital bookkeeping is a safe way to record finances. Although MSME players agree that self-awareness is very important to support the use of digital bookkeeping, the fact is that they face obstacles, including the lack of awareness of individual MSMEs in the importance of the benefits and uses of digital bookkeeping because MSMEs only focus on product innovation. The majority of MSME players do not have experience and knowledge about the importance of online financial records, although they are quite adaptive to technology. With the existence of high individual awareness owned by MSMEs, it can lead to the intention of MSMEs to use digital bookkeeping. This research is inconsistent with research by Saleem et al., (2022) in Pakistan, Singh & Sinha, (2020) in India which shows that personal awareness has an effect on specific technology.

Figure 3. Hypothesis testing result (H1-H4)

Conclusion

This study investigates the impact of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, self-efficacy, and personal awareness on the intention of MSMEs in the Cirebon area to adopt digital bookkeeping. The utilization of digital bookkeeping can assist MSMEs in recording company finances. MSMEs are no longer required to carry out financial records manually due to the implementation of digital bookkeeping. Perceived usefulness and personal awareness were found to have no impact on the digital bookkeeping adoption. The consensus among MSMEs is that with the awareness and confidence of MSMEs in using digital bookkeeping, their financial transaction records are more organized. In addition, due to the easy-to-use interface, MSMEs feel comfortable not worrying about using digital bookkeeping.

This research makes several theoretical contributions through the identification of the determinants that influence the intention to adopt digital bookkeeping. User attitudes are influenced by perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, which in turn have an impact on intention to use, as stated in "TAM". In the proposed model, self-efficacy has a significant impact on users' intention to use digital bookkeeping. While recognizing the importance of individual awareness in supporting the adoption of digital bookkeeping by MSMEs, it is evident that this condition has no effect on MSMEs' intention to adopt digital bookkeeping.

Digital bookkeeping service providers must consistently improve the quality of their products, including application features, because user interest in digital bookkeeping will increase proportionally to the ease of learning and using the application. As a result of technological advances and weak financial management, many MSMEs are still unaware of the importance of cash flow and rarely conduct business planning. The findings of this study are expected to add to the understanding of digital bookkeeping as it relates to Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs).

There are many strengths and limitations to this study. This study used a model with an explanatory power of 66.3%, which indicates that an additional 33.7% can be explained by unexplored variables. A thorough examination of the limitations of this study is essential to ensure the level of applicability of the findings. This study is constrained by its limited geographical coverage, which only focuses on West Java province and, more specifically, Cirebon district and city, which may hinder the applicability of these findings in other areas. Restrictions on education level (many high school graduates) and age range (21-30 years) may hinder the representation of diverse age groups and educational backgrounds among MSMEs. MSMEs that are just starting operations or have been in business for a longer period of time may have perspectives or experiences that are missed due to the emphasis on respondents with around five years of business experience. The responses provided by participants may be skewed towards their own perspectives and experiences, and thus may not accurately represent the overall situation among MSMEs.

Based on the explanation above, the researcher would like to provide some recommendations that are expected to be implemented in future research. In particular, future researchers are expected to expand the scope of their questions to ensure a more

even distribution of respondents, thus producing stronger research results. In addition, future research can explore the relationship between intention to use digital bookkeeping and additional variables, such as education and experience of MSMEs.

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